

Shallow Neural Networks for Channel Estimation in Multi-Antenna Systems

Dheeraj Raja Kumar, Carles Antón-Haro and Xavier Mestre
Centre Tecnologic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Parc Mediterrani de la Tecnologia, Av Carl Friedrich Gauss 7
Castelldefels, Barcelona
{dheeraj.raja.kumar, carles.anton, xavier.mestre}@cttc.es

Abstract—In this paper, we investigate neural network-based channel estimation strategies for point-to-point multi-input multi-output (MIMO) systems. In an attempt to keep computational complexity low, we restrict ourselves to shallow architectures with a single hidden layer. Specifically, we consider (i) fully-connected feedforward neural networks; and (ii) 1D/2D convolutional neural networks. The analysis includes an assessment of the estimation error performance, along with the computational complexity associated to the training and inference phases. Several benchmarks are considered, such as the conventional least squares or (linear) MMSE estimators, and other deep neural network architectures from the literature.

Index Terms—Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network, MIMO, Channel Estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The shift of wireless research focus to B5G/6G has resulted in the progressive introduction of technologies like massive multi-input and multi-output (mMIMO), millimeter wave (mmWave) communications, intelligent reflecting surfaces, interference management via non-orthogonal multiple access schemes, advanced network slicing or network virtualization [1]. All these technologies target a dramatic increase in the number of devices connected to the internet and their growing demand for high throughput.

Obtaining reliable channel state information (CSI) is important for the performance of many signal-processing blocks. Suboptimal (linear) schemes used for this task include linear least-squares (LS) and minimum mean squared error (MMSE) estimation schemes. Alternatively, machine learning (ML) approaches can not only be leveraged to learn non-linear features of the transmission environment, but also achieve better performance at the expense of additional computational complexity. There are various ML schemes ranging from architectures that optimize the different processing blocks separately to techniques that regard the transmitter and receiver as an end-to-end deep neural network (DNN) [2], [3] where the channel estimation task is implicitly carried out.

Among the ML approaches specifically addressing the *channel estimation* process, [4] is designed following the structure of the MMSE channel estimator. The authors build a sample

covariance matrix from the received signal and use it as an input to a neural network (NN)-based estimator. The output acts as a linear filter to calculate the channel estimate. In [5], the time-*frequency* channel matrix is interpreted as an image using a convolutional neural network (CNN). Channel estimation is based on image de-noising, followed by a super-resolution technique performed on the pilot signals. The schemes proposed in this paper are applied to time-*space* channel matrices and employ smaller CNN architectures.

The survey [6] covers a collection of deep learning (DL) based estimators that are designed to refine the output of conventional estimators. These DL-approaches (for both symbol-by-symbol and frame-by-frame estimators) take as input a coarse channel estimate which is derived from conventional estimators (like spectral temporal averaging, data-pilot aided). Our approach works directly on the received pilot signals, which is similar to the approaches discussed in [7] and [8]. The input to the CNN in [7] uses the real, imaginary, and modulus values of the received signal, while the DNNs used in [8] operate separately on the real and imaginary parts. The authors of [8] argue that simpler NN models are necessary to keep the computational complexity of channel estimation in B5G edge networks low. The performance of DNN for channel estimation with limited training samples has been presented in [9]. The paper points out that neural networks with deeper layers may even exhibit inferior performance compared to shallow ones. We extend this approach to study shallow CNN architectures for channel estimation.

Unlike the end-to-end approaches [2], [3], where channel estimation is carried out implicitly, this paper looks at various NN schemes for performing the task at the receiver. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that 1D convolutional neural network (1D-CNN) has been used for channel estimation. In contrast to the CNN models in [5]–[7], the 2D convolutional neural network (2D-CNN) architecture proposed in this paper is kept as shallow as possible to minimize the number of trainable parameters and to avoid the risk of overfitting. We adopt a hybrid approach that leverages on well-established models/architectures, derived from conventional (engineering) approaches, which are enriched by data-driven schemes. The analysis of shallow and deep neural networks is enhanced by studying the computational complexity at both the training and prediction/inference phases.

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II. SIGNAL MODEL AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a point-to-point MIMO system where the transmitter and the receiver are equipped with N_T and N_R antennas, respectively. The received signal corresponding to the transmission of N_P pilot symbols can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{N} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ is the channel matrix and $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times N_P}$ denotes the unit modulus transmit QPSK signals. Finally, $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$ represents the zero-mean i.i.d. additive Gaussian white noise of variance σ^2 . We model the channel as a random matrix with separable covariance, so that one can write $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}}^{1/2} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}}^{1/2}$, where the entries of the matrix \mathbf{G} are modeled as i.i.d. circularly symmetric Gaussian-distributed with zero mean and unit variance and where \mathbf{C}_{Tx} and \mathbf{C}_{Rx} denote the transmit and receive covariance matrices respectively.

In conventional channel estimation, the Least-Squares (LS) scheme computes the channel estimate as

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{LS}} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{X}^H(\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^H)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

The Minimum Mean Squared Error (MMSE) channel estimator with knowledge of the spatial correlation matrices is the optimal estimator for the considered setting in terms of MSE. After some algebra, the estimate can be computed as

$$\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{MMSE}}) = (\mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}}^T \mathbf{X}^* \otimes \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}}) \times \left[(\mathbf{X}^H \mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}} \mathbf{X})^T \otimes \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}} + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R N_P} \right]^{-1} \text{vec}(\mathbf{Y}) \quad (3)$$

where \otimes denotes Kronecker product and where the $\text{vec}()$ operator stacks the columns of a matrix on top of one another. Since the covariance matrices are typically unknown, it is quite common to consider the MMSE under the assumption of uncorrelated channel matrix entries, which takes the form

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{u-MMSE}} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{X}^H(\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R})^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where subindex ‘‘u’’ is used for the uncorrelation assumption. As pointed out above, the implementation of the optimum channel estimator requires perfect knowledge of the channel covariance matrices, which are typically unknown. One of the objectives of this paper is to illustrate how neural networks can overcome this need by implicitly learning the statistical structure of the channel that is to be estimated.

III. NEURAL NETWORK-BASED CHANNEL ESTIMATION

Channel estimation can be modelled as a supervised learning problem. Specifically, it can be cast into a multi-output regression task where:

- The input of the NNs is given by $\mathbf{y} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{Y}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{Y}) \otimes [0, 1]]$. The vector \mathbf{y} is reshaped into different formats depending on the neural network.
- The output of all the NNs is the actual channel response $\mathbf{h} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [0, 1]]$.

The next subsections describe (i) the training set to be used; and (ii) the deep learning schemes considered in this work.

A. Training Set

The training set comprises a total of M examples of input signals $\mathbf{y}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_P \times 1}$ and labels $\mathbf{h}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_T \times 1}$, where $m = 1, \dots, M$.

- 1) Generation of the received signal for a total of M realizations of the communication scenario. For each channel realization, N_P pilot symbols and noise vectors are generated.
- 2) Letting the label of each example to be the actual channel impulse response.

B. Feed-forward Deep Neural Network (DNN)

Feed-forward Deep Neural Networks like the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) can be regarded as universal function approximators. The L -layer MLP consists of: (i) one input layer with $2N_R N_P$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the received signal); (ii) one output layer with $2N_R N_T$ neurons; and (iii) $L - 2$ hidden layers with N_l neurons each, where $l = 2, \dots, L - 1$.

This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_T}$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (5)$$

where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends on the output from the previous layer and also the parameter set of the concerned layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model.

In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. At the output layer, a linear activation function is used as it computes the values of the elements of channel matrix. As for normalization and dropout layers, our proposal does not employ any, as this was found to be counterproductive in most regression problems [10]. In the training phase, the parameter set in each layer is adjusted via stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad, [11]) and backpropagation. The goal is to minimize the mean square error (MSE) loss between the predicted and actual channel impulse response.

C. 1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN)

Unlike DNNs, the weights in Convolutional Neural Networks are arranged in 2-D kernels. They slide over the output of the preceding layer to produce a feature map. In 1D-CNN, the kernel slides only in *one* direction (e.g., along the time axis). This scheme is prominently used for processing time-series data. The pilot symbols sent from the transmitter can be viewed as a time-series, making the application of 1D-CNN suitable for channel estimation.

Here, the size and the number of kernels N_k are the hyper parameters to be tuned. Fig. 1 depicts a particular implementation where the input is of size $N_R \times 2N_P$ (the real and imaginary parts of the received signal). The output of the linear operation of kernels goes through a non-linear activation function. The resulting feature map is typically further reduced

Fig. 1. 1D-CNN for channel estimation.

by the use of pooling layers (e.g., maximum, minimum, or average pooling). However, in this work, we do not use any pooling layers to ensure that all the values in the feature maps generated by the kernels are used for channel estimation. This also helps to avoid overfitting of the models as shown in [9]. In our proposal, we adopt a fully convolutional neural network (FCNN) architecture by which a *single* convolutional layer is followed by the flattening layer, which is then directly connected to the output layer.

Each of the kernels ($1 \dots N_k$) is denoted by $\mathbf{K}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{k_h \times k_w}$, where k_h and k_w stand for the kernel height and width, respectively. The kernel convolves on the input (or previous feature map) $\mathbf{Y}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{h_l \times w_l}$, where h_l and w_l denote its height and width. The generated output feature map $\mathbf{Z}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times (w_l - k_w + 1)}$ can thus be expressed as

$$(\mathbf{Z}_l)_n = \sum_{i=1}^{k_h} \sum_{j=1}^{k_w} (\mathbf{K}_l)_{i,j} (\mathbf{Y}_l)_{i,j+n-1} \quad (6)$$

The training of CNN model [12] involves identifying the kernel weights that are optimized for the regression task.

D. 2D Convolutional Neural Network (2D-CNN)

In 2D-CNN, the kernels typically operate on multiple channels (e.g., red, green, and blue channels, $N_{\text{ch}} = 3$, for color images). Accordingly, in this paper, the received signal is transformed into $N_R \times N_P \times 3$ representation, accounting for the real, imaginary, and phase values of the received signal (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. 2D-CNN for channel estimation.

The kernels in 2D-CNN slide along *both* dimensions, making sweeps first horizontally and the same repeated after

one step vertically. The generated output feature map $\mathbf{Z}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(h_l - k_h + 1) \times (w_l - k_w + 1)}$ can be expressed as

$$(\mathbf{Z}_l)_{k,m} = \sum_{r=1}^{N_{\text{ch}}} \sum_{i=1}^{k_h} \sum_{j=1}^{k_w} (\mathbf{K}_l^{(r)})_{i,j} (\mathbf{Y}_l^{(r)})_{k+i-1, m+j-1} \quad (7)$$

For the task of channel estimation at the receiver, the 2D-CNN is able to extract information along both the time and spatial axes. Typically, this layer is followed by an average pooling layer that downsamples the feature maps. However, similar to 1D-CNN, a flattening layer is used directly after the convolutional layer, followed by the output layer.

IV. PRELIMINARY COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we carry out a preliminary analysis of the computational complexity of the proposed channel estimation schemes. Specifically, we investigate (i) the total number of trainable parameters in the corresponding NN architectures; (ii) the size of required training dataset for a target performance.

A. Total Number of Trainable Parameters

The total number of trainable parameters depends on (i) the number of hidden layers in the NN, which is equal to 1 for all the shallow architectures in this work; (ii) the number of inputs $2N_R N_P$; (iii) the number of neurons at the output layer, which is the total number of real values to be estimated (real and imaginary channel coefficients) $N_L = 2N_T N_R$; (iv) the number of neurons at the hidden layers (N_l) for DNNs; (v) the number of kernels (N_k) and their size which reads $k_h \times k_w$, for CNNs; and (vi) the number of input channels (N_{ch}) which is equal to 1 and 3 for 1D- and 2D-CNNs, respectively. In DNNs, the number of neurons in the hidden layer has a significant impact on the prediction performance. Throughout this work, we let $N_l = N_L$, which translates to the minimum number of neurons required to estimate the associated number of channel coefficients. Having considered all of the above variables, the number of trainable parameters for the three NN architectures can be computed as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
NUMBER OF TRAINABLE PARAMETERS FOR THE DIFFERENT NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURES.

DNN	$2N_R N_T (N_l + 1) + N_l (2N_R N_P + 1)$
1D-CNN	$N_k (N_{\text{ch}} k_h k_w + 1) + 2N_R N_T (N_k N_P + 1)$
2D-CNN	$N_k (N_{\text{ch}} k_h k_w + 1) + 2N_R N_T (N_k N_R N_P + 1)$

Complementarily, Fig. 3 shows the total number of trainable parameters needed for the various NN architectures and across different MIMO configurations. For 1D-CNN and 2D-CNN, we force the number of kernels to be the lowest possible such that the NN-based estimator outperforms the LS/u-MMSE benchmark in terms of normalized MSE (see next subsection). The kernel size for 1D-CNN is set to $k_h \times k_w = N_R \times 2$, whereas for 2D-CNN, we adopt $k_h \times k_w = 3 \times 3$, which is the

Fig. 3. Bar plot showing the total number of trainable parameters for different neural network schemes. The architectures are tuned for optimized MSE performance at 20dB SNR.

commonly used kernel size [7]. As benchmarks, we adopt the NN architectures proposed in [8] and [7], namely, (i) a DNN with 2 hidden layers followed by batch-normalization and dropout layers; and (ii) a 2D-CNN with 2 convolutional layers followed by 1 hidden and dropout layers. The intention is to compare the complexity of shallow versus deep architectures when subjected to a given training dataset size.

The figure (y-axis in log scale) reveals that 1D-CNN employs a similar number of trainable parameters as that of DNNs. However, the number of trainable parameters for 2D-CNNs is substantially higher, in particular for large MIMO configurations. The DNN/CNN benchmarks record at least one order of increase in parameters compared to 1D-CNN. Besides, the number of trainable parameters exhibits an approximately linear increase in the number of transmit/receive antennas for all NN architectures.

The number of trainable parameters has a direct impact on the computational complexity of both the training and prediction phases. A more detailed analysis of computational complexity in the *prediction* phase (in terms of the number of additions and multiplications needed) is carried out in Section V ahead. The complexity in *training* phase also relates to the size of the training dataset, covered in the next subsection. It must be pointed out that the neural networks do not need to be retrained every time the channel changes due to small-scale variations. A single training will be sufficient for much longer time intervals, corresponding to the practical channel stationarity periods.

B. Size of the Training Dataset Required

The computational complexity in the training phase depends on (i) the number of trainable parameters; (ii) the number of epochs needed for reaching convergence/stability; and (iii) the number of examples in the training dataset processed in each epoch.

Concerning (ii) and (iii), Fig. 4 depicts the estimation error as a function of the number of examples in the training dataset. The different NNs are trained for a total of 50 epochs to ensure training convergence. The performance is given in terms of *normalized MSE*, which stands for the MSE per channel coefficient to be estimated. The number of examples

Fig. 4. Channel estimation performance versus training dataset size for a total of 50 training epochs at 20dB.

required for training the different neural networks depends on the MIMO configuration: the higher the number of antennas, the more examples are needed for a target NMSE.

For both MIMO configurations, the architectures requiring the smallest training dataset are the shallow CNNs. Interestingly, the curves reach a floor beyond 10,000 examples for 1D-CNN. For 16x16 MIMO setting (dashed curves), substantially larger dataset are required by DNNs in comparison with 2D-CNNs. In light of the above, for the simulation results in Section V, a training dataset with $M = 70,000$ examples will be used since this guarantees the best performance (lowest NMSE) for most of the NN architectures under consideration.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

We assess the performance of the proposed *channel estimation* schemes based on shallow neural networks by showing results for four different scenarios comprising a MIMO system with $N_T = N_R = 2, 4, 8, 16$ transmit and receive antennas, respectively. The transmit and receive correlation coefficient of the correlation matrices \mathbf{C}_{T_x} and \mathbf{C}_{R_x} are chosen as Toeplitz matrices with n -th diagonal fixed to $0.9^{|n|}$. The dataset (generated using MATLAB) has a total of $M = 10^5$ examples, each comprising $N_P = N_T$ pilot symbols (as this is the minimum number of symbols required to render the problem solvable). Out of the M examples, 20% are used for validation purposes and 10% for testing.

A. Channel Estimation

The architecture of the DNN comprises $L = 1$ hidden layer with a varying number of neurons depending on the MIMO configuration. The input to 1D-CNN is reshaped to a $N_R \times 2N_P$ matrix, while for 2D-CNN, the phase values are computed and the input is reshaped to a $N_R \times N_P \times 3$ tensor. The 1D-CNN kernels are of size $k_h \times k_w = N_T \times 2$ which take strides of 2, whereas the 2D-CNN kernels are of size $k_h \times k_w = 3 \times 3$ taking strides 1, with 1-layer padding along the dimensions of the input image.

A different model is fit for each SNR in the range of -10 dB to 20 dB. For the implementation, training, and evaluation of the proposed schemes, we use Keras on a TensorFlow backend. For the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad), the learning rate is set to 0.01, and a batch size

of 64 samples is used for the computation of the gradient for all the neural networks. The models are trained for 50 epochs to ensure convergence. All the aforementioned parameters are optimized via grid search. As benchmarks, we use, on the one hand, the linear Least Squares estimator, the (optimal) MMSE estimator with knowledge of the spatial covariance matrices, and the (suboptimal) u-MMSE channel estimator given by equations (2), (3), and (4), respectively; and, on the other, the deep NN architectures outlined in Section IV-A, referred to in the sequel as Benchmark-DNN and Benchmark-CNN.

The NMSE performance as a function of the SNR is depicted in Fig. 5 (for smaller MIMO settings) and Fig. 6 (larger ones). The parameters for the various neural networks are outlined in Table II. The architectures (e.g., number of neurons per layer) are tuned for optimized NMSE performance at 20dB SNR.

TABLE II
PARAMETER SETTINGS FOR THE DIFFERENT NEURAL NETWORKS.

MIMO configuration	Parameter	Units
2×2	N_l	8
	$N_{k(1D-CNN)}$	8
	$N_{k(2D-CNN)}$	2
	$N_l(\text{BM-DNN})$	16
	$N_k, N_l(\text{BM-CNN})$	4, 256
4×4	N_l	32
	$N_{k(1D-CNN)}$	16
	$N_{k(2D-CNN)}$	4
	$N_l(\text{BM-DNN})$	64
	$N_k, N_l(\text{BM-CNN})$	8, 512
8×8	N_l	128
	$N_{k(1D-CNN)}$	32
	$N_{k(2D-CNN)}$	8
	$N_l(\text{BM-DNN})$	512
	$N_k, N_l(\text{BM-CNN})$	64, 512
16×16	N_l	512
	$N_{k(1D-CNN)}$	64
	$N_{k(2D-CNN)}$	32
	$N_l(\text{BM-DNN})$	1024
	$N_k, N_l(\text{BM-CNN})$	128, 1024

Clearly, the proposed *shallow* neural networks outperform the LS and u-MMSE benchmarks in all MIMO settings. For the case of 4×4 MIMO, the channel estimation improvement is one order of magnitude at 0dB. Very interestingly, the performance of shallow architectures is virtually identical to that of the optimal MMSE estimator (lower bound) in the low- and mid-SNR regimes; and arbitrarily close to optimal MMSE in the high SNR regime. The explanation for this behaviour lies in the fact that the LS/u-MMSE estimators do not have prior knowledge of the channel distribution (i.e., one-shot estimates are obtained out of the received signal), whereas a large dataset is used to train the NN-based estimators enabling them to empirically learn the statistics of the channel, just like the MMSE estimator does. In other words, they can be regarded as *Bayesian* estimators. The NMSE performance

exhibited by the (deep) Benchmark-DNN and CNN schemes is slightly worse than that of the proposed shallow architectures for smaller MIMO systems and SNRs above 5dB. This is consistent with the findings in [9] and happens despite the fact that (i) their number of trainable parameters is higher (see Section IV-A); and (ii) so is their computational complexity, as it will be discussed in the next section.

Fig. 5. Estimation error for LS, MMSE, u-MMSE and various NN-based channel estimators for smaller MIMO settings. The architectures are tuned for optimized MSE performance at 20dB SNR.

The benefit of using (shallow) 1D or 2D-CNNs vs. (shallow) DNNs becomes clear for higher MIMO configurations. As Fig. 6 reveals, for the 16×16 MIMO scenario, shallow DNNs are not able to offer good estimation performance since for larger MIMO settings they would require larger training datasets (see Fig. 4). 1D-CNN offers similar performance to 2D-CNN using a lower number of trainable parameters. Besides, 1D-CNN also records similar performance to Benchmark-DNN (with two hidden layers). The Benchmark-CNN curves reveal that deep CNNs (two convolutional layers followed by a hidden layer) perform poorly as they also require larger training datasets to offer satisfactory prediction performance. From Table II, we infer that shallow CNNs scale better as the system size grows.

B. Computational Complexity

In the prediction phase, computational complexity of neural networks is determined by the number of operations performed in the forward pass. Fig. 7 shows the number of operations (multiplications and additions) carried out by each of the neural network architectures, compared with the other benchmarks based on the formulae in Table III. The figure (y-axis in log scale) shows that for a given MIMO system, NN-based

TABLE III
COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY OF DIFFERENT CHANNEL ESTIMATION SCHEMES IN THE PREDICTION PHASE.

Variable	LS/MMSE	DNN	1D-CNN	2D-CNN
Number of multiplications in forward pass	$N_R^2 N_P$	$4N_R N_P N_l$	$N_{ch} N_k k_h k_w$ $+ 2N_k N_P N_T N_R$	$N_{ch} N_k N_R N_P k_h k_w$ $+ 2N_R^2 N_k N_P N_T$
Number of additions in forward pass	$N_R^2 (N_P - 1)$	$2N_R N_P + N_l$	$N_k N_{ch} (k_h k_w - 1)$ $+ 2N_R N_T$	$N_k N_R N_P N_{ch} (k_h k_w - 1)$ $+ 2N_R N_T$

Fig. 6. Estimation error for LS, MMSE, u-MMSE, and various NN-based channel estimators for larger MIMO settings. The architectures are tuned for optimized MSE performance at 20dB SNR.

estimators require at least $100\times$ more multiplication and $10\times$ more addition operations than that of LS/u-MMSE estimators. However, this is substantially lower than the number of operations required by Benchmark-DNN/CNN models.

Fig. 7. Number of operations (multiplications and additions) for LS, MMSE, and various NN-based channel estimators.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have investigated the use of shallow neural networks for MIMO channel estimation. Out of the three

shallow approaches proposed for the considered scenarios, 1D-CNN turns out to be particularly interesting. Its performance is similar to that of 2D-CNNs. The computational complexity of 1D-CNN in terms of the number of trainable parameters and additions/multiplications needed for the inference phase is lower. Moreover, 1D-CNNs clearly outperform (shallow) DNNs for larger MIMO systems where the latter are not able to offer good estimation performance. The shallow NNs also outperform other deep(er) NN architectures from the literature and, more importantly, do not exhibit an NMSE floor for the range of SNRs under consideration. When compared with classical channel estimation strategies (LS, MMSE), shallow NNs are able to reduce channel estimation errors by several orders of magnitude. This is due to the fact that, from the training phase they are able to learn the statistics of the channel which are exploited in the inference phase (Bayesian approach). However, this comes at the cost of a substantial increase in computational complexity.

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